

Diffusion Controlled Rates using an Oleophilic Cation Exchange Resin in Non-Aqueous Media

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The rates for diffusion of Na and K from an oleophilic cation exchange resin are studied using tracer technique in non-aqueous media. The parameters investigated included concentration of electrolyte, temperature and radius of the resin. The rate determining mechanism is most probably particle diffusion controlled. The diffusion coefficient of Na in the resin resembles the value for the free diffusion of Na in the corresponding solvent used for the experiment.

THE first ion-exchange resin was synthesized in 1935 by Adams and Holmes. They produced cation exchange resin by condensation of phenol-sulfonic acids with formaldehyde and anion exchange resins by condensing polyamines with formaldehyde; since then resins having physical and chemical properties for specific applications have been produced. Now a days ion-exchange resins are being utilized by a variety of laboratories and industries for separations, recoveries, deionization, catalysis and physico-chemical measurements.

Most of these resins were synthesized to be used in aqueous media, however, few attempts have been made to synthesize ion-exchange resin suitable for uses in non-aqueous media of low dielectric constants. Mayers¹, Kunin² and Gregor³ are among the early pioneers of such studies. One of the authors (M.M.E.) has reported in an earlier investigation⁴, a study on the kinetics of cation oleophilic resins in ethanol.

It is known that the rate determining step of the exchange processes using ion-exchange resins is the film, or particle or a diffusion coupled one. Only in very few cases^{5,6} it has been reported that the rate determining step is the chemical exchange one. Many kinetic studies have been reported in aqueous media and several in mixed solvents. However, very little work has been carried out in pure non-aqueous media. This is due to the very small swelling values of the commercially available resin in pure non-aqueous solvents. The swelling of the newly synthesized oleophilic ion-exchange resin (LS1-4) is very high in ethanol, methanol and several hydrocarbons.

In the earlier investigation⁴, it was shown that these exchange processes using LS1-4 resin in ethanol are quite slow and the data was fitted to chemical exchange rather than diffusion. In doing this two steps were observed, one fast and another slow, and were interpreted as being due to structural effects.

To further substantiate this, one of us⁷ synthesized a new resin with the same characteristics of LS1-4 except for the % of sulfonation (LS1-5). In the latter, the % sulfonation was 80 while the lauroylation % remained the same as in LS1-4 resin (88 %).

Since almost all the aromatic lauroylated rings are sulfonated we would expect to have almost all the sulfonic groups of the same acidity and only one process should have been observed. While conducting the same kinetic experiment of LS1-4 on LS1-5 resin, we observed⁷ that the faster process is indeed diminished but did not completely vanish as one expected. This latter observation made us believe that our earlier explanation, namely, that the rate determining step was the chemical exchange, may not be completely correct. The possibility of having the two steps namely, rates of the chemical exchange and the diffusion exists close to each other although with attendant mathematical complications. The objective of this study is to ascertain whether the rate determining step of metal-metal exchange in pure non-aqueous solvents is diffusion controlled, or not. Therefore, we recalculated the results obtained earlier of the exchange measurements between Na²³ - Na²², Na - K and diethyl amine - H in ethanol using the equations of particle and film-diffusion. Also we extended the experimental measurements to two other temperatures in order to evaluate the activation parameters. The resultant energy of activation falls agreeably in the diffusion range and the data also fitted the particle diffusion equation quite well indicating thereby the plausibility of the latter's choice as the rate determining step in the systems under investigation.

Experimental

Resin characteristics : The beads used are polystyrene with 1% divinyl benzene (DVB) cross-linkage which was purchased from Dow Chemical Company. It was lauroylated using the Friedel-Craft procedure and the lauroylated polystyrene beads were then

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sulfonated. The detailed procedure for the synthesis was reported elsewhere⁷. We give this resin the nomenclature LS1-4. The % of lauroylation was found to be 88 and the % of sulfonation was 47.

The capacity of this resin was found to be 1.26 mellequivalents per dry gram resin, and the swelling in the H-form of the resin in both ethanol and water was found to be 187% and 37% respectively.

Preparation and analysis of the solutions : All the chemicals used in this study were of analytical grades and supplied by Fisher Company; sodium²² chloride was supplied by Nucleonic Corporation of America, New York, U. S. A.

The analysis of Na and K were done by an atomic absorption spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer model 303.

Diethylamine neutralization was carried out using conventional potentiometric titration against HCl.

The radioactive Na²² was assayed by the scintillation Geiger counter nuclear Chicago model No. 1810, which was calibrated using 137 cerium before each run.

Results and Discussion

The rate determining step in ion-exchange process in the present study has been assumed to be the interdiffusion of counter ions either in the resin or across an adherent liquid "film". The slower of these two processes controls the overall rate.

If the diffusion through a bounding liquid film is considered, we find that derived⁸ relationship is

$$F = Q/Q_{\infty} = 1 - e^{-R^2 t} \quad \dots (1)$$

where Q = the amount of counter ion on the resin at any time t ; Q_{∞} = the total amount absorbed at equilibrium and $R = 3D/r\delta k$, where D is the diffusion coefficient in the film; r is the radius of the resin beads; δ is the thickness of film; k is the distribution coefficient and is defined by $C' = KC^{\circ}$, where C' and C° are the equilibria concentrations in the solid and liquid respectively.

If, however, the diffusion out of a spherical particle is considered the following equation can be obtained,

$$Q/Q_{\infty} = 1.08 \sqrt{Bt} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $B = D'\pi^2/r^2$, D' being the diffusion coefficient through the particle.

We now apply both types of equations (1) and (2) to our data and the results will be presented for the three systems used, namely (a) H^+ -Diethylamine reaction, (b) Na-K exchange and (c) Na²²-Na²³ exchange.

(a) H^+ -Diethylamine reaction : In this case the resin was in the hydrogen form and the diethylamine was in the bulk solution. The reaction was carried out using two concentrations of amine at 25°. Also the size of the resin was varied and two radii were used. Equations (1) and (2) were fitted

to the experimental data separately. The plots of Bt vs t and $-\log(1-F)$ vs t are shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that the particle diffusion equation fitted the data better than the film diffusion equation, at the two concentrations used. The diffusion coefficients D in the particle is $1.4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ when diethylamine was $0.1M$ and $1.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ when its concentration was $0.085M$.

Fig. 1. Bt vs t and $-\log(1-F)$ vs t for diethylamine - H results-using LS 1-4 resin.

Diethylamine Absorption in ethanol at 24-25°
 I—0.108M Amine ○ Particle diffusion × Film diffusion
 II—0.085M Amine ● " " ⊗ " "

(b) Na-K exchange : Here the resin was in the sodium form and the bulk solution contained potassium acetate and the aliquots of the solution at various times were analyzed for Na using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Two concentrations of K acetate were used ($0.1M$ and $0.2M$) at 25°. Applying equations (1) and (2) for these two concentrations, we find, as shown in Fig. 2, that the two equations fitted the data at the earlier part of the curve. The diffusion coefficients in the particle was found to be $1.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and 3.1×10^{-10} when the concentration of K acetate was $0.1M$ and $0.2M$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Bt vs t and $-\log(1-F)$ vs t for Na-K exchange results using LS1-4 resin.

Na-K Exchange in ethanol at 24-25° LSI-4 resin
 ○ 0.1M K Acetate (Particle diffusion)
 × 0.2M " "
 ● 0.1M K Acetate (Film diffusion)
 ⊗ 0.2M " " " "

Fig. 3. $\log (1-F)$ vs t for $RNa^{22} - Na$ at $25, 35$ and 45° using $0.04 M$ sodium acetate.
 $Na^{22} - Na^{23}$ Exchange $0.048M$ "Film diffusion"

(c) $Na^{22} - Na^{23}$ exchange: In this study one size (0.169 mm in the dry form) of resin LS1-4 was used while the other two parameters were varied. Measurements at three temperatures $25^\circ, 35^\circ$ and 45° were carried out using $0.048M$ sodium acetate in the bulk while the resin was tagged with Na^{22} . The results obtained by applying the equation of film diffusion, eq. (1), to the cases at the three temperatures, are plotted in Fig. 3. For the particle diffusion equation (2) the corresponding results are shown in Fig. 4. The process was repeated for concentrations, $0.012M$ and $0.024M$ sodium acetate, other at 25° and equations 1 and 2 were fitted to them. The resultant plots are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Bt vs t for $RNa^{22} - Na$ at $25, 35$ and 45° using $0.04 M$ sodium acetate.

$Na^{22} - Na^{23}$ Exchange $0.048M$ "Particle diffusion"

Table 1 summarizes the results under the above five conditions when $RNa^{22} - Na^{23}$ exchange was taking place and particle diffusion eq. (2) was used. The energy of activation was calculated from the temperature dependence of the particle diffusion coefficient and was found to be 3.98 kcal/mole.

Fig. 5. Bt vs t and $-\log (1-F)$ vs t for 0.012 and $0.024 M$ sodium acetate at 25° .

$Na^{22} - Na^{23}$ Exchange
 Film diffusion \square $0.012M$ Particle diffusion \otimes $0.012M$
 " " \triangle $0.024M$ " " ∇ $0.024M$

TABLE 1— $Na^{22} - Na^{23}$ EXCHANGE USING LS1-4 IN ETHANOL UNDER VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS AND TEMPERATURES USING Eq. (2) FOR ANALYSIS. $R=0.0169$ cm.

Concn.	$t^\circ C$	$1/T \times 10^{-3}$	$C \times 10^{-6}$	$D' \times 10^{-11}$	$\log \Delta'$
0.012	25°	—	399	4.019	—
0.024	25°	—	2.5	7.2945	—
0.048	25°	3.96	3.0556	8.842	-9.94656
0.048	35°	3.25	3.338	9.6459	-9.8102
0.048	45°	3.15	4.445	12.861	-9.10924

$\Delta E=3.98$ kcal/mol.

It is interesting to note that eventhough both equations (1) and (2) fitted the data, however, the diffusion coefficients were found to be constant in case of eq. (2) indicating thereby that the data is better fitted to eq. (2). It is also found that the energy of activation of diffusion as obtained by fitting the particle diffusion equation (i.e., eq. 2), at the three temperatures used, falls nicely in diffusion controlled reactions range.

The above findings indicate that our assumption that the particle diffusion is the rate determining step appears most likely to be the correct one.

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